

Job Satisfaction of Contract of Service Employees in a Government Agency: Basis for an Action Plan

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Abstract

The study aimed to investigate the satisfaction of COS employees (Contract of Service) who were working in a government agency in Central Philippines during Quarter 2 of 2023. In doing so, the researcher collected quantitative data from 124 respondents using a reliable research instrument they developed. Consequently, they examined the age, sex, civil status, and eligibility as independent variables. At the same time, they measured job satisfaction in three areas: working conditions, compensation and recognition, and career development opportunities. Reliably, the respondents were chosen through purposive sampling. Based from the results, it showed that most respondents were young, male, single, and did not have civil service eligibility. In general, they reported high job satisfaction in all these areas. However, there were some differences in working conditions, with

tenured, male, married, and non-eligible employees reporting higher satisfaction. Compensation and recognition were rated highly by most, with only small differences by sex and eligibility. Career development opportunities also received high ratings, no matter the respondents' backgrounds. In addition, statistical analysis found no significant differences in working conditions based on age, sex, or civil status, but there was a significant difference based on eligibility. Also, the compensation and recognition, and career development opportunities signified no significant differences by age or civil status, but there were significant differences by sex and eligibility. In a nutshell, these findings revealed the need to improve job stability, strengthen compensation and recognition systems, and offer training programs in helping employees gain civil service eligibility and move forward in their careers.

Keywords: *Job Satisfaction, Contract of Service, Government Agency, Working conditions, compensation and recognition, career development opportunities, Civil service eligibility, Descriptive Study, Action Plan*

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Nature of the Problem

A job consumes most employees' lives as they spend 8 hours or more fulfilling their duties and responsibilities, affirming that employees are the key element in an organization. Thus, employee satisfaction is vital to the organization's success. Job satisfaction affects employees' productivity, career development, and work-life balance. It is an employee's perspective, reflecting how they feel about their job and the organization they work for (Abuhashesh et al., 2019).

Among employees working in different organizations, there is a need to understand the perspective of contract of service (COS) employees. According to the Inventory of Government Human Resources as of June 30, 2022, 642,077, or roughly 26% of the total government workforce, consisted of Job Order and Contract of Service personnel (SBN-1703, 2023). Contract of Service employees are considered self-employed and not in an employer-employee relationship. In this thesis, COS refers to individuals with technical and specialized skills hired for a special project or job with minimal supervision for a maximum period of one (1) year, with possible renewal. They differ from Job Order workers, who are hired for piecework (pakyaw) or for short-duration emergency jobs. However, most of their contracts have been renewed every year, resulting in months to years spent in the organization, holding degrees and licenses, yet their future remains unpromising. Working eight hours or more to fulfill their duties without the benefits of permanent employees, as their services are not considered government service. Moreover, COS employees are not covered by Civil Service law, rules, and regulations, as they are not considered government employees (CSC-COA-DBM Joint Circular No. 1, s. 2017).

The researcher was a COS worker for more than four (4) years before becoming a regular (plantilla) employee in 2023. Despite this transition, she has observed that, to date, the working conditions, compensation, recognition, and career development opportunities of COS workers, as well as the government's plans for them, have remained uncertain and unfavorable. Many COS workers continue to wait for regularization while facing the possibility of retrenchment. Some are single, and some are married and already have a family – yet have not been regularized due to the limited number of available regular positions relative to the growing number of COS personnel in the organization. These instances motivated the researcher to conduct this study, as they could serve as a basis for recommendations and for crafting an action plan that may help improve the morale, well-being, and working conditions of COS workers across various branches of the government and its instrumentalities.

B. Current State of Knowledge

Job satisfaction is based on how we feel about our job – the good career components that make us feel valued or let us feel like we have a purpose, vs. the bad components, such as long hours or unpleasant tasks, or feeling undervalued as an employee according (FutureLearn, 2022). Despite their contributions to the organization, temporary workers have been seen as secondary. Moreover, there has been limited research on the topic regarding temporary workers (Lopes & Chambel, 2014).

The widespread practice of contractualization has reduced workers' control over their working conditions and environment, as well as lowered job satisfaction and motivation. In the worst case, the responsibility for determining which organization addresses employment concerns has left workers confused. Precarious work is implemented through contractualization, with temporary workers replacing regular employees who will not be entitled to seniority rights, benefits, or job security (Cristobal, M. A. E. A., & Resurreccion, E. II K., 2014).

Contractual jobs are a type of non-standard employment in which workers lack permanent status. This can create challenges in work conditions and emotional responses to the job. The study suggests that job satisfaction is influenced not just by pay and conditions, but also by how work arrangements impact work-life balance and psychosocial well-being. This indicates that satisfaction for contractual workers is complex, involving both job experiences and their lives outside of work (Lagrana & Bayoneta, 2021).

Baqi and Indradewa (2021) found a significant difference in pay, job status, and length of service between permanent and temporary contract employees, with permanent employees reporting higher job satisfaction. Factors such as educational attainment, skills, training, and years of work experience may lead to higher pay for individuals. Also, well-paid workers were likely to stay in the organization longer. On the other hand, due to employment uncertainties, employees under contract have lower job satisfaction.

Compared to permanent employees, temporary workers often have less access to training and career development opportunities, which is linked to lower job satisfaction and organizational connection (Burgess & Connell, 2022). Moreover, Lomoya, Pingol, and Teng-Calleja (2015) on Antecedents of Job Satisfaction among Contractual Workers highlight how job characteristics, such as workload and autonomy, along with training and development opportunities, are linked to job satisfaction, even for contractual employees. It points out the importance of intrinsic job factors in shaping satisfaction. The study also notes that the lack of job security and rewards in contractual systems can lead to different behavioral patterns among these workers. Furthermore, COS workers feel excluded from decision-making and organizational activities, which further lowers their satisfaction.

Waaiker, Belder, and Sonneveld (2017) examined how temporary contracts and job characteristics affect job satisfaction and personal lives. It shows that an education level is necessary for the job, as it influences job satisfaction. The authors found that individuals employed in positions requiring lower educational qualifications than they possess negatively affect the workers' job satisfaction. This means working in positions that do not match an employee's educational level lowers job satisfaction.

COS employees are generally not required to have Civil Service Eligibility since they are employed on a temporary, limited-purpose, or project basis and do not have an employer-employee relationship with the government. The lack of eligibility usually acts as a major obstacle to obtaining permanent employment, which can lead to a more secure job and benefits. As temporary workers, they are usually not entitled to Government Service Insurance System (GSIS), PhilHealth, Pag-IBIG (except for voluntary membership), or government bonuses (such as mid-year or year-end bonuses). The study suggests that eligibility for these benefits directly influences the motivation and level of job satisfaction of these workers (Estacion et al., 2023).

C. Theoretical Underpinnings

Job satisfaction can be regarded as a conclusion derived from the comparison between what employees actually receive from work and their expectations, desires, and perceived entitlements (Gomes, 2016). This study is anchored on Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, developed by Frederick Herzberg in 1959. Based on this, people's job satisfaction depends on two factors: hygiene and motivation.

According to Herzberg, hygiene factors are not motivators. Motivational factors lead to positive satisfaction that are inherent to work. These factors involved in performing the job satisfy employees' needs for growth and self-actualization and are intrinsically rewarding. Motivational factors include recognition, opportunities for development and growth, responsibility, and meaningfulness of the work.

In contrast, hygiene factors are also called dissatisfiers or maintenance factors, which are extrinsic to the job and are essential for the existence of motivation at work. Secondary working conditions that do not lead to positive satisfaction in the long term. However, if these factors are absent, dissatisfaction results. Hygiene factors represent the basic physiological needs that individuals expect to have satisfied. Hygiene factors include physical working conditions, salary, benefits and allowances, company policies and administrative policies, interpersonal relations, and job security.

Finding a job is not easy; what is more, staying in an organization without a stable career path that leads to utmost satisfaction is even harder. This framework works well for this study because this theory helps better understand the perspectives of contract service workers and their drive toward the job. For contract of service (COS) workers in the Philippine government, motivation factors include recognition and career development opportunities, which are intrinsic to the job because they help satisfy employees' needs for growth and self-actualization. On the other hand, hygiene factors include work conditions and compensation, which are extrinsic to the job and are essential in preventing dissatisfaction but do not necessarily lead to long-term motivation. The theory suggests that while good hygiene factors keep a satisfactory work environment for COS employees, motivational factors play a bigger role in improving their overall job satisfaction and work engagement.

D. Objective of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of job satisfaction of Contract of Service (COS) employees in one government agency in the Central Philippines during the Second Quarter of Calendar Year 2023, as a basis for an action plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the profile of the respondents according to the variables age, sex, civil status, and eligibility; 2) the level of job satisfaction of Contract of Service (COS) employees according to the areas working conditions, compensation and recognition, and career development opportunities; 3) whether a significant difference exists in the level of job satisfaction of COS employees when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and, 4) the formulation of an action plan based on the findings of the study.

II. RESEARCY METHODOLOGY

This section presents a discussion of the research methodology used, the subject-respondents of the study, the research instrument used, the validity and reliability of the instrument, the procedure for data gathering, conduct of the study, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

A. Research Design

This study aimed to determine the level of job satisfaction of contract-of-service employees in one government agency in the central Philippines for Calendar Year 2023, as a basis for an action plan. Descriptive research aims to systematically describe the characteristics of a population or phenomenon as it exists, without manipulating the variables in the study (Creswell, 2014).

Using this research design, the researcher was able to gather and analyze data on respondents' levels of job satisfaction across working conditions, compensation and recognition, and career development opportunities. In addition, the study examined whether job satisfaction levels differ across age, sex, civil status, and eligibility. Finally, the research design enabled the identification of the prevailing problems contributing to low job satisfaction, which served as the basis for formulating an action plan.

B. Study-Respondents

The respondents of the study were gathered from the Office Memorandum on the Renewal of Contract of Services/Job Orders for Workers/Pakyaw of the GOCC's Luzon, Visayas, and Mindanao offices for the year 2023. The respondents in the study are Contract of Service (COS) employees of the Visayas office, with a total population of 182. From the total population of 182, 124 contracts of service (COS) were selected as the respondents of the study using the Cochran formula (1977).

Due to the large study population, the researcher used purposive sampling to select respondents. This technique was used because the study specifically focused on Contract of Service (COS) employees who were directly relevant to the research objectives. Respondents were purposely chosen from those assigned in the different offices in the Visayas. To enhance the relevance and validity of the collected data, purposive sampling ensured that only individuals with appropriate employment status and direct experience were included.

C. Instrument

The researcher gathered the necessary data for this study by constructing a research-designed survey questionnaire to ensure reliability. The questionnaire was divided into two parts, with part I focusing on the respondents' profiles in terms of age, sex, civil status, and eligibility. Part II of the questionnaire covers 30 items that assess the level of job satisfaction of contract of service employees, with 10 items for each of the following area: working conditions, compensation and recognition, and career development opportunities. The researcher used both face-to-face and Google Forms to disseminate the survey questionnaires. A link was generated and provided to respondents to access the survey online, particularly to the COS assigned to field offices for convenience. Then, the results were exported through MS Excel. Each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 = always, 4 = often, 3 = sometimes, 2 = rarely, and 1 = almost never.

D. Data Gathering and Procedure

After administering the validity and reliability tests, the researcher submitted a formal letter to the agency's Administrator through the Human Resource Division, requesting permission to conduct the study and collect the necessary data. Once approval was granted, the researcher presented the authorized request letter to the Department Managers and Supervisors of the Visayas Office. Data collection was conducted through a combination of face-to-face and online platform (Google Forms) for respondents assigned in field offices. Respondents are provided with clear instructions on how to complete the survey questionnaire, and a one (1)-month period, covering only working days, is allotted for them to answer the instrument. After retrieval, the data were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted in accordance with the study's specific objectives.

E. Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive-analytical scheme, frequency count, and percentage scoring to determine the profile of respondents. Objective No. 2 used the descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of respondents' job satisfaction. Objectives No. 3 used the comparative-analytical scheme, Mann Whitney U, and Kruskal-Wallis H tests to determine if a

significant difference exists in the level of job satisfaction of contract of service employees when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

F. Ethical Considerations

The researcher ensured that respondents provided informed consent and voluntarily participated in this study; no identities were disclosed, ensuring full confidentiality and protection of the data, given the nature of the relationship between the government agency and the respondents. The data gathered was handled properly and responsibly to prevent misuse and unauthorized access, as well as to avoid any linkage of personal information. All information collected was used solely for this research. Any data, activity, or procedure that could potentially cause harm to any individual or institution was excluded and not performed.

III.RESULT and DISCUSSION

In this section, the data gathered were further treated, presented, analyzed, and interpreted to focus on the study's specific objectives.

A. Profile of Respondents

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 45 years old)	75	60.50
	Older (45 years old and above)	49	39.50
	Total	124	100
Sex	Male	79	63.70
	Female	45	36.30
	Total	124	100
Civil Status	Single	76	61.30
	Married	48	38.70
	Total	124	100
Eligibility	Non-eligible	60	48.40
	1st Level Eligibility	3	2.40
	2nd Level Eligibility	31	25.00
	Eligibility under Special Laws	30	24.20
	Total	124	100

This study surveyed 124 contract of service employees to provide a clearer understanding of the personal backgrounds of the respondents that may influence perceptions of job satisfaction. The demographic variables considered include age, sex, civil status, and eligibility.

As presented, the majority of respondents (60.50%) are below 45 years old, while 39.50% are aged 45 years and above. In terms of sex, male respondents dominate the survey with 63.70%, while 36.30% are female. As for the respondents' civil status, 61.30% are single, and 38.70% are married. Lastly, there is a notable diversity in the data on civil service eligibility. Nearly half of the respondents reported having no formal eligibility (48.40%), while 25.00%

reported second-level eligibility. Meanwhile, 24.20% hold eligibility under special laws, and a small fraction, 2.40%, possess first-level eligibility.

In summary, the majority of contract of service employees are single males under 45 years old, with mixed civil service eligibility, with nearly half lacking eligibility.

Descriptive Analysis of the Level of Job Satisfaction of Contract of Service Employees in a Government Agency

Table 2

Level of Job Satisfaction of Contract of Service Employees in Working Conditions

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Working Condition		
1.The orientation about the organization in general and my job description are complete and timely.	4.46	High Level
2.The organization provides all the equipment, supplies, and resources necessary to perform my job.	4.41	High Level
3.The working conditions are safe and conducive to productivity.	4.52	Very High Level
4.The workload is manageable and appropriate for my position.	4.47	High Level
5.The reporting structure is very easy and clear between me and my superiors.	4.49	Very High Level
6.I feel secure of my job in the organization.	4.11	High Level
7.My colleagues are collaborative and respectful.	4.53	Very High Level
8.The supervisor is approachable and supportive.	4.73	Very High Level
9.The supervisor provides clear and constructive feedback on my performance.	4.54	Very High Level
10.The work-life balance is appropriate and manageable.	4.42	High Level
Overall Mean	4.47	High Level

Table 2 shows the Level of job satisfaction of contract of service employees in the area of working conditions, which obtained an overall mean of 4.47, interpreted as “High Level”. Moreover, item 8, “the supervisor is approachable and supportive,” earned the highest mean score of 4.73, interpreted as “Very High Level.” In contrast, item 6, “I feel secure in my job in the organization,” obtained the lowest mean of 4.11, interpreted as “High Level.”

This implies that contract service employees are afraid of losing their jobs, since they are temporary workers in the government sector without an employer-employee relationship. They are under contracts that can be renewed at the agency's head's discretion; thus, their goals for job satisfaction are to obtain stable jobs or long-term career growth. This also means that despite their employment status, they have built good relationships with their superiors. Their supervisors are easy to speak with and provide assistance and support, which contributes to a strong aspect of their working environment. Job security, on the other hand, is highly rated but still requires attention to ensure COS employees feel valued and have peace of mind at every renewal, as they do not enjoy the usual employment security and other benefits of regular (plantilla) positions.

This conforms with CSC-DBM-COA Joint Circular No. 1, s. 2017, which states that government agencies may enter into contracts of service with individuals as consultants/contractors, subject to the guidelines. The term of contract between the agency and the individual contractor shall be for a maximum period of one year, renewable at the option of the head of the procuring entity. In effect, these workers are not covered by the Civil Service laws, rules, and regulations, as they are under a contract (memorandum of agreement); hence, the services rendered to their employer, irrespective of the years, are not recognized as government service.

Table 3
Level of Job Satisfaction of COS Employees in the Compensation and Recognition

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Working Condition		
1.The orientation about the organization in general and my job description are complete and timely.	4.46	High Level
2.The organization provides all the equipment, supplies, and resources necessary to perform my job.	4.41	High Level
3.The working conditions are safe and conducive to productivity.	4.52	Very High Level
4.The workload is manageable and appropriate for my position.	4.47	High Level
5.The reporting structure is very easy and clear between me and my superiors.	4.49	Very High Level
6.I feel secure of my job in the organization.	4.11	High Level
7.My colleagues are collaborative and respectful.	4.53	Very High Level
8.The supervisor is approachable and supportive.	4.73	Very High Level
9.The supervisor provides clear and constructive feedback on my performance.	4.54	Very High Level
10.The work-life balance is appropriate and manageable.	4.42	High Level
Overall Mean	4.47	High Level

Table 3 reflects the level of job satisfaction of contract of service employees in the area of compensation and recognition. The respondents’ perceptions of how effectively and fairly the organization compensates and recognizes its workforce, with an overall mean of 3.81, indicating a high level of effectiveness and fairness. The highest mean was on item 1, “My compensation is fair and competitive compared to similar positions in other organizations,” with a mean of 4.31, interpreted as a high level, while the lowest mean was on item 4, “The organization provides incentives or rewards for exceptional performance,” with a mean of 3.35, interpreted as a moderate level.

This implies that, despite the efforts, time, and hard work invested by contract of service (COS) employees in performing their jobs, outstanding performance is not consistently rewarded. As a result, this lack of recognition will not increase employee motivation and retention. It has also been shown that COS employees believe the agency’s compensation is fair and competitive compared to similar positions in other organizations. However, COS employees’ service is not

classified as government service, so they are not entitled to the benefits regular employees enjoy, such as bonuses, incentives, leave privileges, and allowances. Additionally, COS employees still require an extra source of income; these incentives could help them purchase necessities and support their families. This points to the need for better support for COS employees, as we cannot fully understand the challenges each faces in pursuing a stable livelihood.

The findings agree with the study by Sambo (2018), which found that the salaries of service contractors or contract service employees typically align with standardized salary rates for government employees, which they regard as rather equitable, but they lack job security. Therefore, they are not entitled to paid vacation, sick leave, and maternity leave for women, while sanctions are imposed for tardiness and absences. Thus, most still believe they are underpaid because they cannot claim overtime pay and are denied bonuses and incentives granted only to regular government employees, despite the extent of their services/responsibilities.

Table 4

Level of Job Satisfaction of COS Employees in the Area Career Development Opportunities

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Career Development Opportunities		
1.The organization provides opportunities for professional growth and development.	4.21	High Level
2.The organization provides opportunities for career advancement.	4.10	High Level
3.The organization encourages me to pursue training or educational programs to enhance my skills and knowledge.	4.11	High Level
4.The organization provides mentoring or coaching to support my career development.	4.11	High Level
5.The organization provides opportunities for me to learn new skills or take on new responsibilities.	4.29	High Level
6.The organization provides clear career paths and advancement opportunities.	4.10	High Level
7.The organization provides support for continuing education or professional certifications.	4.18	High Level
8.The organization provides opportunities for me to participate in projects or initiatives outside of my regular job duties.	4.07	High Level
9.I receive constructive feedback on my performance to help me improve and grow in my role.	4.18	High Level
10.I am provided with opportunities to take on new responsibilities or challenging projects that contribute to my professional development.	4.21	High Level
Overall Mean	4.16	High Level

Table 4 shows the level of job satisfaction of contract of service employees in the area of career development opportunities, with an overall mean of 4.16, interpreted as a high level. It also revealed the highest mean on item 5, "The organization provides opportunities for me to learn new skills or take on new responsibilities," with a mean of 4.29 interpreted a high level while the lowest mean was on item 8, "The organization provides opportunities for me to participate in projects or initiatives outside of my regular job duties," with a mean of 4.07, interpreted as high level.

This implies that COS employees do not have sufficient opportunities to participate in the organization's extracurricular activities beyond their job assignments. This situation may cause them to feel less valued in participating in organizational programs, consultative meetings, and interdepartmental projects that could enhance their professional development. This also shows that while the agency permits COS personnel to develop their skills and potential through training and mentoring focused solely on their current workloads, opportunities for involvement beyond regular job duties are highly valued but occur less frequently. Therefore, limited, selective engagement in broader initiatives contributes to lower satisfaction among COS employees.

This aligns with the study by Van der Klink et al. (2015), which found that temporary workers received fewer opportunities to boost their employability than permanent employees due to employment arrangements. Furthermore, according to CSC-DBM Joint Circular No. 2, s. 2020, COS personnel are not covered by the training and development programs intended for regular employees.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Job Satisfaction of Contract of Service Employees in a Government Agency

Table 5

Difference in the Level of Job Satisfaction of COS Employees in Working Conditions

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	75	61.65	1774.000		0.744		Not Significant
	Older	49	63.80					
Sex	Male	79	63.77	1677.500		0.602		Not Significant
	Female	45	60.28					
Civil Status	Single	76	60.93	1705.000		0.540		Not Significant
	Married	48	64.98					
	Non-eligible	60	69.38					
Eligibility	1st Level Eligibility	3	108.00	11.699		0.008	0.05	Significant
	2nd Level Eligibility	31	57.44					
	Eligibility under Special Laws	30	49.42					

The difference in the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees in the Area Working Conditions, when they are grouped and compared according to Age, obtained a p-value of 0.744, according to Sex, obtained a p-value of 0.602, and according to Civil Status, with a p-value of 0.540, which are greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no significant difference in the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees when grouped and compared according to the variables of age, sex, and civil status in the area of Working Conditions” is accepted. On the other hand, when the variable Eligibility groups them, the p-value is 0.008, which is lower than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no significant difference on the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees when grouped and compared according to the variable of eligibility in the area of Working Conditions” is rejected.

This indicates that, regardless of age, gender, or marital status, the difference is not significant. Since they generally share the same physical workplace, resources, and environment, they thus experience equal exposure to organizational policies and workplace culture.

Eligibility, on the other hand, influences how COS employees are treated, valued, and positioned in the organization. COS employees with eligibility under special laws reported the lowest satisfaction because, having passed professional examinations, they expect greater opportunities, recognition, and job assignments. However, their expectations are not fully met due to the nature of COS employment, where they face the same working conditions as other personnel. Moreover, employees with second-level eligibility are qualified for higher-level positions; they also have high expectations but experience a lower level of satisfaction due to limited job security and benefits. Additionally, non-eligible respondents show higher satisfaction, as they have fewer expectations and have accepted their current work arrangements. Due to their lack of civil service eligibility, they cannot demand better working conditions and a favorable working environment. As a result, they deliver what is asked of them. Finally, employees with first-level or sub-professional eligibility report the highest satisfaction, as their roles match their eligibility and their current job responsibilities align with regular entry-level positions, giving them an advantage should these positions open for hiring.

This aligns with the study by Anastasiou and Garametsi (2021): job satisfaction was not significantly affected by marital status or other personal characteristics such as sex or socio-economic status, but education was. Because education shapes expectations, competence, and the alignment of an employee's goals with their work environment, these factors are more important for satisfaction than fundamental demographic traits. Moreover, COS and JO workers may hold the same job for years, but they cannot advance to a regular position without civil service eligibility (Sambo, 2018). However, Aquino (2023) points out that civil service eligibility is a distinguishing characteristic among agency-hired employees: some possess it, while others do not, yet both groups remain non-permanent personnel. The study indicates that eligibility does not guarantee regularization or a permanent position. Thus, insofar as it is a key qualification, it is not the only organizational factor that determines employment stability among agency-hired workers.

Table 6
Difference in the Level of Job Satisfaction of COS Employees in Compensation and Recognition

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	75	61.33	1749.500		0.652		Not Significant
	Older	49	64.30					
Sex	Male	79	69.04	1261.000		0.007		Significant
	Female	45	51.02					
Civil Status	Single	76	62.32	1810.000		0.943		Not Significant
	Married	48	62.79					
	Non-eligible	60	74.19					
Eligibility	1st Level Eligibility	3	39.83	14.730		0.002	0.05	Significant
	2nd Level Eligibility	31	58.58					
	Eligibility under Special Laws	30	45.43					

The difference in the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees in the Area Compensation and Recognition, when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables of age, yielded a p-value of 0.652, and for civil status, a p-value of 0.943, both of which are greater than the level of significance 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no significant difference in the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees when grouped and compared according to the variables of age and civil status in the area Compensation and Recognition” is accepted. In contrast, when the variables sex and eligibility group them, the p-values are 0.007 and 0.002, respectively, which are lower than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no significant difference in the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees when grouped and compared according to the variables of sex and eligibility in the area of Compensation and Recognition” is rejected.

This implies that variables of age and civil status in the study do not create meaningful differences among COS employees. Temporary workers often perform similar tasks regardless of their age or civil status, resulting in minimal salary variation and affecting the recognition they receive. In addition, they do not receive benefits or incentives from the agency; therefore, they experience equal exposure to the same employment conditions.

In contrast, sex and eligibility matter; agency work typically involves fieldwork. Men are usually given these job assignments because, biologically, they have upper-body strength to

handle tasks requiring lifting and carrying field supplies and equipment. Moreover, men usually have endurance for long hours of sun exposure and other weather conditions, even though women are equally capable. Fieldwork, however, involves transportation, sanitary facilities, and maternity needs. This allows men to visibly contribute to the agency's programs and functions, leading to more recognition from supervisors and colleagues. On the other hand, female COS employees are often assigned to administrative and support roles, making their contributions less visible than those of male employees and resulting in lower salaries and less recognition. Therefore, sex influences perceptions of fairness in pay and recognition.

In terms of eligibility, COS employees with first-level eligibility reported the lowest satisfaction, as they usually work in clerical positions with higher workloads that consume more time and energy. As a result, they expect greater recognition and better salaries with benefits. Moreover, those eligible under special laws were moderately satisfied with their pay and recognition, as they remain employed as COS despite qualifications that could lead to better pay and regularization. The same is true for respondents with second-level eligibility, who exhibit even lower levels of satisfaction. In contrast, COS employees without civil service eligibility obtained the highest satisfaction, as they have lower expectations for benefits and pay and have accepted their current work arrangements. Although eligibility is not required for temporary work, its absence limits the chances of non-eligible personnel to obtain regular employment in the government, except for positions that do not require eligibility, such as utility workers. As a result, they perceive their current salary as satisfactory despite the limitations of COS employment.

The study's results aligned with those of Mateo-Fernando et al. (2022), who found that men placed greater importance on factors such as compensation and benefits, a comfortable workplace, the need to support their families, and being good at their current jobs. They mostly care about tangible rewards, while women place the most value on using their skills and abilities, on the meaning of their work, and on their relationships with coworkers and bosses. On the other hand, this study aligns with Estacion et al. (2023), who found that COS employees are generally not required to have Civil Service Eligibility, as they are employed on a temporary, limited-purpose, or project basis and do not have an employer-employee relationship with the government. The absence of eligibility usually acts as a major obstacle in obtaining permanent employment, where they will have a more secure job and benefits. As temporary workers, they are usually not entitled to Government Service Insurance System (GSIS), PhilHealth, Pag-IBIG (except for voluntary contributions), or government bonuses (such as mid-year or year-end bonuses). The study suggests that eligibility for these benefits directly influences the motivation and level of job satisfaction of these workers.

Table 7

Difference in the Level of Job Satisfaction of COS Employees in Career Development Opportunities

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	75	59.90	1642.500		0.317		Not Significant
	Older	49	66.48					
Sex	Male	79	67.86	1354.000		0.027		Significant
	Female	45	53.09					
Civil Status	Single	76	63.61	1739.500		0.663		Not Significant
	Married	48	60.74					
	Non-eligible	60	72.87					
Eligibility	1st Level Eligibility	3	62.50	11.108	0.011	0.011	0.05	Significant
	2nd Level Eligibility	31	57.10					
	Eligibility under Special Laws	30	47.35					

Table 7 on the difference in the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees in the Area Career Development Opportunities, when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables of age and civil status, revealed p-values of 0.317 and 0.663, respectively, which are greater than the level of significance 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no significant difference in the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables of age and civil status in the Area Career Development Opportunities” is accepted. However, when grouped by sex, it revealed a p-value of 0.027, and for eligibility, 0.011, both of which are lower than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that “there is no significant difference in the level of Job Satisfaction of the Contract of Service Employees when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables of sex and eligibility in the Area Career Development Opportunities” is rejected.

This suggests that, in terms of career opportunities, age and civil status are insignificant, whereas sex and eligibility create differences. Male COS employees report higher satisfaction than their female counterparts, as they are often given field assignments and provided with training and seminars essential to performing their jobs, particularly in implementing programs or projects; however, these opportunities are generally limited to their regular duties. In contrast, women are also offered opportunities for career development; however, these opportunities are not frequently provided by the agency, resulting in lower job satisfaction.

In terms of eligibility, COS employees with eligibility under special laws obtain the lowest satisfaction. As holders of professional licenses, they expect more training and development opportunities. However, in reality, these are typically provided to permanent employees, leaving them underutilized and undervalued despite their credentials. Similarly, respondents with second-level eligibility also report low levels of satisfaction. Moreover, first-level eligible employees may feel satisfied, as they are also allowed to attend training and seminars for professional development. However, work arrangements for temporary workers focus more on output delivery than on workers' growth. As a result, despite already possessing eligibility, they expect more career advancement programs. In contrast, non-eligible respondents expressed satisfaction despite the limited growth opportunities. They have lower expectations because they have understood and accepted their situation. As a result, when they are given opportunities to participate in training and additional responsibilities, they feel valued and thankful that, despite not having civil service eligibility, the agency still includes them, which thus contributes to higher satisfaction.

The results contradict the study by Fernando and Vargas (2021), which found no association between career advancement and sex. Regarding professional growth, statistical research found no correlation between sex and job satisfaction, indicating that male and female employees assess these factors similarly. This supports the notion that, in terms of job satisfaction, career development factors are valued by everyone and are not dependent on sex. Eligibility findings conform with the CSC, DBM Joint Circular No. 2, s. 2020, which states that COS workers are not eligible for the same training and development programs as regular government workers, because COS workers are temporary or contract workers, they do not automatically receive career development benefits like regular employees do. The circular does not require any training for COS personnel; it is optional for the agency.

IV. ACTION PLAN

This part presents a strategic action plan to improve the job satisfaction of COS employees in a Government Agency.

Introduction

This portion presents the proposed action plan, developed based on the study's findings regarding the level of job satisfaction among COS employees. The results revealed that, due to the nature of COS employment, they are considered self-employed and lack an employer-employee relationship; thus, they face limitations in job security, benefits, civil service eligibility, and professional advancement. If not addressed, the agency may encounter difficulties in retaining employees and utilizing their skills. These challenges highlight the need for a structured action plan to promote fairness, improve morale, job satisfaction, and working conditions for COS employees.'

General Objectives

The purpose of this action plan is to provide COS employees with fair opportunities for job security, recognition, and career development while promoting fairness, transparency, and efficiency within the institution. Specifically, the plan aims to:

1. Provide stable employment to qualified COS employees by proposing the creation of new regular plantilla positions for functions that are necessary, regular, and recurring, thereby addressing job insecurity.
2. Ensure allocation of funds to support the implementation and sustainability of the created plantilla positions, including the payment of salaries and benefits.

3. Provide additional compensation and recognition measures to motivate COS employees.
4. Develop training programs that support COS employees in enhancing skills, learning, and service delivery through obtaining civil service eligibility credentials.

ACTION PLAN

Areas of Concern	Findings	Objectives	Activities	Time Frame	Budget	Person Involved	Success Indicator
Working Conditions	The study found that item 6, "I feel secure in my job in the organization," had the lowest mean.	Provide stable employment opportunities for qualified COS employees.	Prepare and submit a proposal to create new regular plantilla positions for qualified COS employees performing necessary, regular, and recurring functions. Include staffing patterns, justification, and accomplished forms outlining the duties and responsibilities of the new positions. Submit a proposal for approval.	1 year	3,600,000	Agency Head, Agency Officials, Human Resource Unit, Budget Office, Governing Board	Approval of proposed positions; Number of plantilla positions created
		Ensure funding support for the creation of new regular plantilla positions.	Allocate funds for salaries and benefits; prepare and submit budget proposals;			Budget Unit, Finance Unit, Agency Head	Budget approved; Funds allocated for new positions.

Compensation and Recognition	The study found that item 4, "The organization provides incentives or rewards for exceptional performance," had the lowest mean.	To recognize and reward the contributions and dedication of COS employees while enhancing motivation, morale, and job satisfaction.	Provide cash gifts or recognition incentives as a voluntary initiative of the government agency, which is subject to the availability of funds and existing regulations.	Annually	455,000	Agency Heads, Agency Officials, Budget Officials, Human Resource Officials	Increased motivation and job satisfaction of COS employees as reflected in employee feedback and satisfaction surveys
Career Development Opportunities	The study found that item 8, "The organization provides opportunities for me to participate in projects or initiatives outside of my regular job duties," had the lowest mean.	Increase the number of eligible COS employees to promote greater professional growth and strengthen their capacity to qualify for eligibility and career advancement.	Implement Human Resource-led programs to assist COS employees in obtaining eligibility credentials (review sessions, mentoring, exam support)	Semi-annually	500,000	Human Resource Officials	An increase in the number of COS passing the Career Service Examination

V. CONCLUSION

The COS employees in the organization primarily consist of single males aged 45 years and younger who do not possess civil service eligibility.

A contract binds the nature of employment for a COS employee. They are considered self-employed because an employer-employee relationship doesn't exist, and their service in the government, regardless of the number of years, is not considered government service. However, despite these circumstances, they still exhibit positive job satisfaction by mostly scoring high across all variables in working conditions, compensation and recognition, and opportunities for career development.

Tenured COS employees expressed more favorable evaluations of their working conditions, as they have greater experience and more realistic expectations than younger COS employees. However, regardless of age, COS employees are highly satisfied with compensation, recognition, and career development opportunities.

The level of satisfaction of male COS employees is higher than that of their female counterparts in working conditions, compensation, and recognition, reflecting a male-dominated organization in which fieldwork, appreciation, pay, and leadership styles tend to favor men. In contrast, both sexes are highly satisfied with career development opportunities.

Married COS employees expressed greater satisfaction with working conditions than single COS employees, as they have greater family responsibilities; thus, they value regular working hours, supportive supervisors, and a safe working environment. On the other hand, regardless of civil status, COS employees are pleased and satisfied with compensation and recognition, as well as opportunities for career development.

The level of satisfaction among COS employees varies by eligibility; those with 2nd-level and special eligibility anticipate better working conditions. Similarly, those with 1st-level and special eligibilities presume higher compensation and recognition; thus, not meeting these expectations resulted in lower satisfaction than those COS employees with lower eligibilities. Moreover, career development opportunities positively influence job satisfaction, regardless of eligibility.

The level of job satisfaction of COS employees is relatively similar across age and civil status in the three areas. However, variations arise in sex and eligibility: satisfaction levels in working conditions are affected by eligibility, whereas satisfaction levels in compensation, recognition, and career progression are influenced by sex and eligibility. These indicate that sex and professional qualifications are important variables that determine how COS employees perceive and experience work, whereas age and civil status have only a minimal influence.

REFERENCES

- Abuhashesh, S., Al-Dmour, H., & Masa' deh, R. (2019). Factors that affect employees' job satisfaction and performance to increase customers' satisfactions. *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 2019, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.5171/2019.354277>
- Anastasiou, S., & Garametsi, V. (2021). Perceived leadership style and job satisfaction of teachers in public and private schools. *International Journal of Management in Education*, 15(1), 58–77. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMIE.2021.111817>
- Aquino, M. J. M. (2023). Job stability and agency-hired employees' satisfaction in a government-owned and controlled corporation. *Multidisciplinary International Journal of Research and Development*, 3(1), 61–79.
- Burgess, J., & Connell, J. (2020). *Precarious employment: Understanding labor market insecurity in a global context*. Routledge.
- Baqi, F.A. & Indradewa, R. (2021). The effect of compensation on job satisfaction of permanent employees and contract employees, Department of Human Resources Management, Faculty of Economy and Business, Esa Unggul University, Jakarta, Indonesia. <https://www.aijbm.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/P48144151>
- Civil Service Commission, Commission on Audit, & Department of Budget and Management (2017). *Rules and regulation governing contract of service and job order workers in the government*. <http://csc.gov.ph/2014-02-21-08-28-23/pdf-files/category/926-csc-coadbm-joint-circular-no-1,-s-2017>
- Cochran, W. G. (1977). *Sampling techniques (3rd ed.)*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Commission on Audit, Department of Budget and Management (2020). *Updated rules and regulations governing contract of service (cos) and job order (jo) workers in the government*. <https://www.dbm.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/Issuances/2020/JointCircular/COA-DBM-JOINT-CIRCULAR-NO-2-S-2020.pdf>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (4th ed.)*. Sage Publications.
- Cristobal, M. A. E. A., & Resurreccion, E. I. (2014). *De-confusing contractualization: Defining employees engaged in precarious work in the Philippines*. *Phil. LJ*, 88, 342.
- Estacion, T. D. L., Moredo, J. A. S. N., Nebreja, M. R. N., Pabico, F. G., Popan, K. A. C., Talagtag, R. S., & Terrado, K. D. (2023). *Level of motivation and job satisfaction of selected job order employees in the City Government of Santa Rosa, Laguna: Basis for new compensation policies* [Undergraduate thesis, Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Santa Rosa Campus]. ResearchGate. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14026.54725>
- Fernando, M. C. M., & Vargas, D. S. (2021). *Importance of career development and satisfaction of job contract employees amidst pandemic (COVID 19) at the Central Luzon State University* (Working paper). SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3824944>
- FutureLearn. (2022, October 18). *The future of work: What you need to know*. FutureLearn. <https://www.futurelearn.com/info/blog/the-future-of-work-what-you-need-to-know>

- Gomes, J. F. (2016). *Job satisfaction and its determinants in the workplace*. Journal/Publisher.
- Herzberg, F. (1959). *Two-Factor Theory of Motivation*.
- Lagrana, L. R., & Bayoneta, M. J. A. R. (2021). The relationship between job satisfaction and work life balance of non standard employment (NSE) workers of a manpower agency. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 4(1), 83–96. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v4i1.318>
- Lomoya, M. G., Pingol, M. B., & Teng Calleja, M. (2015). Antecedents of job satisfaction and organizational citizenship behaviors among agency hired blue collar contractual workers in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Psychology*, 48(1), 1–27.
- Lopes, S., & Chambel, M. J. (2014). Motives for being temporary agency worker: Validity study of one measure according to the self-determination theory. *Social Indicators Research*, 116(1), 137–152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-013-0273-3>
- Mateo Fernando, M. C., Porciuncula, F. L., Galindez, J. L., Vargas, D. S., & Fernando, J. G. (2022). A gender centered analysis on mutuality of work values and satisfaction of hired agri-based functionaries in a state university during the pandemic period: Bridging the divide. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(5), 6629–6644. <http://journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/8190>
- Sambo, H. Q. R. (2018). *Government workers beyond the boundaries of labor laws*.
- Senate Bill No. 1703. (2023). 19th Congress. *An Act Providing for the Grant of Security of Tenure for All Casual and Contractual Employees of the Government Who Have Rendered the Prescribed Length of Service and for Other Purposes*. Senate of the Philippines. <https://legacy.senate.gov.ph/lisdata/4039436801!.pdf>
- Van der Klink, J. J., Bültmann, U., Burdorf, A., Schaufeli, W. B., Zijlstra, F. R., Abma, F. I., Brouwer, S., & van der Wilt, G. J. (2015). Sustainable employability – definition, conceptualization, and implications: A perspective based on the capability approach. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*, 42(1), 71–79. <https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.3531>
- Waaiker, C. J. F., Belder, R., Sonneveld, H., van Bochove, C. A., & van der Weijden, I. C. M. (2017). *Temporary contracts: Effect on job satisfaction and personal lives of recent PhD graduates*. *Higher Education*, 74(2), 321–339. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-016-0050-8>